

BIOT COEFFICIENTS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBRE PACKED ASSEMBLIES: EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL

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SUMMARY

The present paper aims at predicting the Biot coefficients for perfectly straight unidirectional (UD) fibre assemblies using micromechanical methods: Mori–Tanaka and Ponte Castañeda–Willis estimates. An experimental procedure, based on both uniaxial and triaxial material testing machines, is also detailed and applied to rubber fibre assemblies. The theoretical and experimental Biot coefficient results are compared and show a good agreement.

Keywords: Unidirectional fibre reinforcement; Porous media; Biot coefficients; Poromechanics; Microporomechanics; Composite manufacturing

1. INTRODUCTION

Processing composites often involves either the compression of pre-impregnated fibre reinforcements or the flow of a viscous liquid within fibrous materials. The moulding pressures during the process can reach high levels due to the compaction of the fibres getting closer to each other and the fibrous media permeability drop because of the fibre volume fraction rise. The lower mechanical performances and microstructure of vegetal fibres compared to traditional synthetic fibres raise the question of the effect of such moulding pressures on the structural integrity of the fibres.

Usually, when the compression of impregnated fibrous media is involved, Terzaghi's equation is used. This soil mechanics result relates the total stress tensor of an impregnated porous media as the function of the stress tensor applying on the porous skeleton and the interstitial liquid pressure. However, when the constituents deform due to their own compressibility under hydrostatic pressure, it is necessary to introduce the Biot tensor to take this effect into account.

2. POROMECHANICAL THEORY AND TESTS

2.1. Impregnated Porous Media

Due to analogies between granular and fibrous media [13], researchers have been using Terzaghi's equation in previous composite manufacturing studies, where compression of impregnated fibrous media is involved [7, 8,11]. This soil mechanics result (Eq. (1)) relates the total stress tensor Σ of an impregnated porous media as the function of the stress tensor applying on the porous skeleton Σ' and the interstitial liquid pressure P

$$\Sigma = \Sigma' - \delta P \quad (1)$$

where δ is the second-order unit tensor

$$\delta_{ij} = 1 \text{ if } i = j; \quad \delta_{ij} = 0 \text{ if } i \neq j \quad (2)$$

When the constituents deform due to their own compressibility under hydrostatic pressure, it is necessary to introduce the second-order Biot tensor B in Terzaghi's relationship

$$\Sigma = \Sigma' - BP \quad (3)$$

The Biot tensor components are positive, inferior to one and B is diagonal [2]

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & b_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & b_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

b_1 , b_2 and b_3 are the three components of the Biot tensor in the three respective Cartesian coordinates.

For most soils, the grains are supposed infinitely rigid compared to the material they form, thus the Biot tensor reduces to the second-order unit tensor (Terzaghi's hypothesis). Using results from poroelasticity, the Biot tensor can be expressed as function of the fourth-order drained homogeneous elastic tensor C_{hom} (stiffness tensor) of the skeleton and of the fourth-order elastic compliance tensor S_f of the constituent [3]

$$\mathbf{B} = \delta(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{S}_f : \mathbf{C}^{hom}) \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the fourth-order unit tensor

$$I_{ijkl} = \frac{1}{2}(\delta_{ik}\delta_{jl} + \delta_{il}\delta_{jk}) \quad (6)$$

The main work for the calculation of the Biot tensor consists in the calculation of the \mathbf{C}_{hom} tensor. For fibre assemblies of interest in this study, the Biot tensor's components can be considered within two particular cases of symmetry:

- both fibre assembly and individual fibre are isotropic (the case of glass mat, for example). In this case, $b_1 = b_2 = b_3 = b$, and the well-known relation (see, e.g. [2]) applies

$$b = 1 - \frac{k^{hom}}{k_f} \quad (7)$$

where k^{hom} and k_f are the bulk moduli of the homogeneous (fibrous) material and the individual fibre, respectively;

- the fibre assembly is transversely isotropic with an axis of revolution Ox_3 and the individual fibre is isotropic. The transverse isotropy is only due to the presence of inter-fibre aligned pores. In this case [5]

$$b_1 = b_2 = 1 + \frac{1 + \nu_{31}^{hom}}{3k_f \left(\frac{2(\nu_{31}^{hom})^2}{E_3^{hom}} - \frac{1 - \nu_{21}^{hom}}{E_1^{hom}} \right)}; \quad b_3 = 1 + \frac{E_3^{hom} \left(\frac{2\nu_{31}^{hom}}{E_3^{hom}} + \frac{1 - \nu_{21}^{hom}}{E_1^{hom}} \right)}{3k_f \left(\frac{2(\nu_{31}^{hom})^2}{E_3^{hom}} - \frac{1 - \nu_{21}^{hom}}{E_1^{hom}} \right)} \quad (8)$$

where E_3^{hom} , E_1^{hom} , ν_{31}^{hom} and ν_{21}^{hom} are the elastic moduli and the Poisson ratios of the drained homogeneous material.

The relations of the Biot coefficients (Eq. (8)) are calculated as a function of homogeneous moduli and Poisson ratios which are unknown, therefore specific tests will be performed so as to measure them.

2.2. Tests on the rubber fibre samples

To obtain the Biot coefficients through experimentation for the transversely isotropic material, tests have been realized on the rubber fibre samples. The fibres (5 mm in diameter) are made of nitrile butadiene rubber whose Young modulus is 15 MPa and Poisson ratio is 0.48.

In the present work, the Biot coefficients are measured for the two arrangements of unidirectional rubber fibres: square and hexagonal (Fig. 1). The unidirectional rubber fibres are assembled and lightly glued together to maintain the arrangement during the test and to assure the straightness of the fibres. The Biot coefficients of the square and hexagonal fibre arrangement materials are calculated with Eq. (8).

Figure 1. Square (left) and hexagonal (right) arrangements.

The determination of the Biot coefficients (square and hexagonal fibre arrangements) require to measure five moduli: the bulk modulus of the fibre k_f ; the elastic moduli and the Poisson ratios of the drained homogeneous material E_3^{hom} , E_1^{hom} , ν_{31}^{hom} and ν_{21}^{hom} . The direction Ox_3 is oriented along the axis of the fibre. The various moduli (Tab. 1) will be measured through several tests (Tab. 2). When the experiment requires one, the confinement liquid used is water.

Table 1. Test types and corresponding moduli.

UD compression	E_3^{hom} , E_1^{hom}	ν_{21}^{hom}
Shear	ν_{31}^{hom}	
Drained isotropic compression	k^{hom}	
Undrained isotropic compression	k_f	

Table 2. Samples geometry and test conditions.

Tests	UD compression	Isotropic compression	Shear
Diameter	50 mm	50 mm	50 mm
Height	50 mm	100 mm	50 mm
Compression speed	0.2 mm/min	6 kPa/min	0.1 mm/min

2.2.1. Unidirectional compression tests

The square and hexagonal arrangement samples are tested with a unidirectional compression machine to measure the homogeneous elastic moduli E_3^{hom} and E_1^{hom} . The slope of the quasi linear parts of the stress vs. strain curves gives the tangent moduli E_3^{hom} and E_1^{hom} .

2.2.2. Shear tests

The shear test and the isotropic test are realized with a triaxial machine (originally used for soils). The impregnated sample is confined in a membrane which isolate it from the confinement water. The shear test allows to measure two parameters: the elastic modulus (E_3^{hom} and E_1^{hom}) and the Poisson ratio ν_{31}^{hom} . During the test, the displacement of the piston (strain ε_3 or ε_1), the axial effort (stress σ_3 or σ_1) and the water volume ejected or brought in the cell (volumetric strain ε_v) are measured. The elastic moduli E_3^{hom} and E_1^{hom} are determined from those data. The infinitesimal volumetric strain writes:

$$\varepsilon_v = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \quad (9)$$

Moreover, for the shear test in the Ox_3 direction, $\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_2$, which leads to

$$\varepsilon_1 = \frac{\varepsilon_v - \varepsilon_3}{2} \Leftrightarrow \nu_{31}^{hom} = \frac{\varepsilon_1}{\varepsilon_3} = \frac{\varepsilon_v}{2\varepsilon_3} - \frac{1}{2} \quad (10)$$

where the values of the volumetric strain ε_v and the strain ε_3 (in the Ox_3 direction) are given by the shear test. The Poisson ratios ν_{31}^{hom} are determined with Eq. (10).

The Poisson ratio ν_{21}^{hom} cannot be determined directly by shear test. It is determined using the drained bulk modulus k^{hom} , which is measured by an isotropic compression test.

2.2.3. Isotropic compression tests

The isotropic compression test is also realized with the triaxial machine. The sample is prepared and confined as in the shear test, the amount of confinement water which enters or leaves the cell as function of the isotropic confinement pressure is considered as the deformation of the rubber sample (for drained test) or the deformation of the fibre rubber itself (undrained test). The drained homogeneous bulk modulus k^{hom} is calculated as the ratio of the isotropic confinement compression rise to the volumetric strain ε_V of the drained test, whereas the undrained bulk modulus k_f (or the fibre bulk modulus) is calculated from the undrained test.

Thanks to the moduli k^{hom} , E_3^{hom} , E_1^{hom} and the Poisson ratio ν_{31}^{hom} , the Poisson ratio ν_{21}^{hom} is determined by the relation for the transversely isotropic material

$$\nu_{21}^{hom} = 1 - \frac{E_1^{hom}}{2} \left[\frac{1}{k^{hom}} - \frac{1}{E_3^{hom}} (1 - 4\nu_{31}^{hom}) \right] \quad (11)$$

2.2.4. Results

The curve of the Biot coefficients and their mean values of the square and hexagonal arrangements are presented in Fig. 2 and in Tab. 3, respectively. Firstly, the Biot coefficients are clearly lower than one. This shows that the Terzaghi's hypothesis (Biot coefficient is equal to one) may not be applied for all cases of saturated fibrous materials.

Figure 2. Biot coefficients of the square and hexagonal arrangements.

Then, for the same arrangement, the Biot coefficients b_1 (in the weakest modulus direction Ox_1) are always superior to b_3 (in the highest modulus direction Ox_3). This shows the influence of the material structure on the Biot coefficients. Moreover, for the same direction of two different structures, the Biot coefficients of the square

arrangement are always slightly superior to that of the hexagonal arrangement. Finally, the Biot coefficients decrease when the applied stress is raised.

Table 3. Experimental mean values of the Biot coefficients.

	b_1	b_3	porosity
Square	0.837	0.793	0.215
Hexagonal	0.746	0.682	0.093

3. MICROPOROMECHANICAL APPROACH

3.1. Background

The estimated Mori–Manaka [3] and Ponte Castañeda–Willis [10] schemes will be studied. They are calculated based on the Eshelby tensor S_E or Hill tensor P which are determined analytically [4,9,12] with inhomogeneities of the ellipsoidal shape (three principal semi-axis a_1 , a_2 and a_3). The S_E and P tensors can be also calculated numerically for the general case of the ellipsoidal inhomogeneity with an arbitrary orientation [5,6]. The solutions of two above estimated schemes will be compared to choose the adapted schemes.

The first scheme studied is the one derived by Mori–Tanaka. It accounts for the mechanical interaction between pores. The porosity in the Mori–Tanaka scheme can reach up to 20% [1], the individual fibre is considered as the reference medium. The homogeneous stiffness tensor for the Mori–Tanaka scheme is (see, e.g. [3])

$$C_{MT}^{hom} = (1-c)C_f : \left((1-c)I + c(I - P : C_f)^{-1} \right)^{-1} \quad (12)$$

where c is the porosity; C_f is the fourth-order stiffness tensor of the fibre; P is the Hill tensor, $P = S_E : S_f$, S_E is the Eshelby tensor which depends on both the geometry of the inhomogeneity and the reference medium.

The second scheme studied is the Ponte Castañeda–Willis estimate which, furthermore, takes into account the spatial distribution of the pores through a distribution function. The development of this scheme is based on the variational formulation of Hashin and Shtrikman, and the reference material is always taken identically to the individual fibre. For the case where all the pores have the same orientation, the homogeneous stiffness tensor of the Ponte Castañeda–Willis scheme writes (see, for more details [10])

$$\mathbf{C}_{PCW}^{hom} = \mathbf{C}_f + \left(\frac{1}{c} (\mathbf{P}_i - \mathbf{S}_f) - \mathbf{P}_d \right)^{-1} \quad (13)$$

Here \mathbf{P}_i is equivalent to \mathbf{P} in the previous scheme (it characterizes the shape of the pores) while \mathbf{P}_d characterizes the spatial distribution of the pores in the material.

3.2. Application to unidirectional fibre assemblies

The fibre assembly has been modelled with the following assumptions:

- it is linear elastic;
- it consists of aligned, parallel, linear elastic and isotropic fibres;
- it is modelled with cylindrical pores.

To facilitate calculation with fourth-order tensors, the Walpole basis is used [1,14]. The ellipsoidal pores are considered cylindrical for both schemes. The pores distribution in the Ponte Castañeda–Willis scheme is circular (readers may refer to [10] for more details).

The homogeneous stiffness tensors \mathbf{C}_{MT}^{hom} and \mathbf{C}_{PCW}^{hom} of the two schemes are determined using Eqs. (12)–(13). The results obtained are then substituted in Eq. (5) to calculate the Biot tensor.

The calculations lead to the following results for the Biot coefficients for the two schemes. In the case of the Mori–Tanaka scheme

$$b_1^{MT} = b_2^{MT} = \frac{2c(1-\nu)}{1-2\nu+c}; \quad b_3^{MT} = \frac{c[1+c(1-2\nu)]}{1-2\nu+c} \quad (14)$$

and for the Ponte Castañeda–Willis scheme, the Biot coefficients are

$$\begin{aligned} b_1^{PCW} = b_2^{PCW} &= \frac{6c(1-\nu)[2c(4-5\nu)+15(1-\nu)]}{4c^2(1+\nu)(4-5\nu)+c(60\nu^2-99\nu+57)+45(1-\nu)(1-2\nu)} \\ b_3^{PCW} &= \frac{3c(1-\nu)[4c(4-5\nu)+15]}{4c^2(1+\nu)(4-5\nu)+c(60\nu^2-99\nu+57)+45(1-\nu)(1-2\nu)} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The Biot coefficients of the transversely isotropic material, which has isotropic constituents, only depend on the porosity c and the Poisson ratio ν of the constitutive fibre. The modulus of the fibre cancels out during derivations.

4. THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL COMPARISON

The results of the Biot coefficients of the two schemes are presented in Fig. 3 with a Poisson ratio ν equal to 0.48. The curve of the Mori–Tanaka scheme tends towards one when the porosity tends towards one, the Ponte Castañeda–Willis scheme for the circular distribution of the fibre is not much different to the Mori–Tanaka, except the fact that the Biot coefficients is only approximated to one when the porosity tends towards one. For the very low values of porosity, the three schemes give almost identical Biot coefficients. The value of b_1 is always greater than that of b_3 .

The experimental mean values of the Biot coefficients for the square and hexagonal arrangements (Tab. 3) are also presented in Fig. 3 as function of the initial porosity with the theoretical curves of the Mori–Tanaka and Ponte Castañeda–Willis schemes.

A rather good agreement between the theoretical and experimental results has been found.

Figure 3. Theoretical and experimental results of the Biot coefficients, with $\nu = 0.48$.

5. CONCLUSION

Experimental Biot coefficients for unidirectional fibre assemblies have been obtained following a procedure that involved uniaxial and triaxial testing machines. Micromechanical schemes have also been used and combined to the poromechanical theory in order to obtain Biot coefficients of unidirectional fibre assemblies. Both micromechanical and experimental results are in good agreement.

The theoretical results are based on the assumptions of isotropy and perfect straightness of the fibres. That first result is somehow limited to some applications, but it is a starting point for former evolutions towards the reality of composites manufacturing. It suggests that the Biot coefficients of a UD assembly of isotropic fibres are lower than one and that Terzaghi's assumption is not valid for this specific case. Improvements should take into account specificities such as the transverse isotropy of fibres, and localized contacts, finite and non-linear deformations of fibre assemblies.

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